
Problem Encountered by EFL University Students in Translation English Proverbs

Abdelbadie Ahmed Ibrahim¹, Lecturer in English– Jazan
University,abdelbadie1966@gmail.com

Yassir Elgailani Ahmed², Lecturer in English – Jazan University abumazen700@gmail.com

Dr. Abdelrahman Mohammed Elhassan Hamid³, Lecturer in English – Jazan University
Abomhmoud1930@gmail.com

Paper Received on 11-04-2024, Accepted on 09-05-2024
Published on 11-05-24; DOI: 10.36993/ RJOE.2024.9.2.122

Abstract:

This study is concerned with the problems encountered by EFL University students in translating English proverbs into Arabic. The main hypothesis of the study is that there is a wide range of problems posed to Arab EFL University students and translators when rendering English proverbs. Examining such problems is the precept aim of the study. It also aims to answer these questions

- 1- What are the appropriate strategies for solving the problems of translating proverbs?
- 2- Why do some students lack knowledge about proverbs?
- 3- Why do great orators' resort to proverbs and idioms in their speech?

A translation test was conducted to identify types of errors and translation mistakes made by EFL students and translators, besides a questionnaire.

The results revealed that there are in fact many problems encountered by EFL students and translators when dealing with English proverbs. The most important aspect of these problems is the failure to achieve the natural equivalents of such proverbs. Clearly, erroneous errors such as literal translation, wrong translation minimizing proverbs to sense and breaching of the Arabic language system along with hidden erroneous errors such as using paraphrasing and using dialects, were the major reasons behind the failure of producing the appropriate equivalents for the proverbs listed in the translation test.

Keywords: Translation, Proverbs, paremiology, Strategies of translations, Problems of translation proverbs.

Introduction:

Translation studies are a new discipline that has expanded massively in recent years. Academic research is still needed in this area. Written and spoken translations have played a vital role in communication, not least in providing access to important texts for scholarship and religious purposes. Translation has a great role in interchanging human being cultures, economic, and social fields, translation also narrows the gap between nations and cultures all over the world, hence the world lives in diversity and this diversity can be narrowed through intercultural and transferring knowledge from one area to another and from one country to another, and so on, so many Organizations deal with the process of translation, the practice of translation was crucial for the early dissemination of key cultural and religious texts concepts.

While the practice of translation is long established, the study of the field developed into an academic discipline only in the latter part of the twentieth century. Before that translation had often

Research Journal Of English(RJOE)

ISSN:2456-2696;An International Peer-Reviewed and Refereed Journal;Impact Factor:8.16 (SJIF)

Indexed in: Cosmos, Google &International Scientific Indexing (ISI) etc

been relegated to an element of language learning a new language or reading a foreign language text until one had the linguistic ability to read the origin. Nowadays, translation is becoming a necessity for people worldwide to understand each other, cultural, educational, political, economic, and situational backgrounds. Translation has many branches written translation and spoken translation.

The translator must have a thorough mastery of the target language as well as a very good passive understanding of the source language or languages.

Statement of the problem

There are many problems in the translation process encountered by ESL students, especially in translating proverbs, and the researcher attributes this to many reasons, the students are not well acquired in proverbs of the source language, lack inter-culture, the students are not widely studied the proverbs in the disciplinary in the Universities, so if those problems are not solved the process of translating proverbs may be affected negatively through conveying a wrong message from the source language to the target language.

Thus the researcher tries to deal with new strategies to contribute to solving these problems that face the students when they translate in the field of proverbs.

Objectives of the study

This research aims to shed light on the difficulty that students face when translating proverbs.

- 1- To study the reasons that lead the students to commit mistakes and errors while translating proverbs.
- 2- To find out the appropriate strategies to overcome these problems of translating proverbs.
- 3- To explore the speeches used by orators and prophets in their speeches.

Questions of the study

- 1- What are the appropriate strategies that can be discussed to solve the problems of translating proverbs?
- 2- Why do some students lack knowledge about proverbs?
- 3- Why do great orators resort to proverbs in their speech?

Hypothesis of the study

- 1- Use appropriate strategies in teaching proverbs for EFL learners, to be aware of using them.
- 2- Translating proverbs reinforces meaning-based translation.
- 3- Proverbs are precisely and eloquently worded. When solemnity is sought, speakers and writers resort to them.

Significance of the study

This study is an attempt to investigate the difficulties that the translators and the students of translation encounter while they are studying at post-graduate levels in translating proverbs. This study might also help translators and students to know how to deal with proverbs. It is expected to contribute to designing a curriculum and syllabus in this field to help translators and students deal with proverbs in the future.

Methodology of the study

The analytical descriptive method will be followed in conducting this study. Besides, a questionnaire to collect the required data.

Population of the study

A sample of (50) students of translation will be chosen randomly from the target population to participate in this study. The researcher might give the population certain types of proverbs.

Tool for data collection

The tool for collecting data for this research will be a questionnaire for (50) students who are studying translation focusing on many types of proverbs.

Data analysis

The data will be analyzed by (SPSS) program by calculating the percentage of the mean and the standard deviation.

Review of theoretical literature

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Translation, culture, and types of proverbs.

Definition of the proverb Many experts and theorists define proverbs in various meanings, one of these scholars and theorists is Katherine Murphy(proverbs.P.13, liturgical Press 2013). She stated that proverbs represent the ongoing search for a way of being in the world that is life-giving and fruitful, they illuminate the different realities and circumstances that human beings experience while being mindful of the presence and activity of God. In proverbs, aphorism is a search that each person must undertake for him or herself. Aphorism is above all an endeavor. While Ernest Lucas (P.2- published by William B.Erdmans publishing company Cambridge. UK) mentioned that the exact sense of the word proverb is not obvious. It could be related to a verb meaning "to rule" and so mean a word that gives mastery, or a powerful word. Alternatively, it could become a verb meaning "to be like" and so mean comparison, whether explicit or "similes" or implicit "metaphor". James D. Martin/Eilen F. Davies (P.13 Westminster John Knox Press), said that proverb expresses the main values and perceptions that characterize a community through many generations. They are a key to the community's stable identity, and precisely this makes them valuable in times of transition and crisis. The Concise Oxford Dictionary of Proverbs written by Speake(2008), states that a proverb is a traditional saying that offers advice or presents a moral in a short and pithy manner.

Honeck (1979) maintains that proverbs could be used in literary topics such as poetry and prose...etc., because of the aesthetic and passional values they carry like Shakespeare's (Measure for Measure) which is translated into Arabic الصاع بالصاع او رد الصاع صاعين. Owoanogela (2009) stated that proverbs share all the devices in English poetry like meter, rhyme, assonance and alliteration, metaphor, occasional inverted word orders, unusual construction, and personification. The second use is a practical one, proverbs could be used in daily life for many situations because of their shortness and the indirect message they contain as well as the aphorism they have.

According to Barajas (2010), proverbs are expressions that are framed by contradictions because they are sage expressions that refer to something palpable to express things that are not specific. Furthermore, the obscure proverbs do not weaken them but allow them to become popular social aphorisms. Moreover, despite proverbs being considered popular expressions, few people can use them correctly in conversations with social and linguistic skills. In addition, although proverbs have fixed forms, their meanings could be changed according to the interpretation of particular social factors and settings.

According to Carter (2002, P.68), proverbs have formal and semantic characteristics in common. They carry some kind of aphoristic truth, usually in simple present tense, and are normally neither syntactically devisable nor substitutable.

Meider(1985, P.119) has defined proverbs as " a short, generally, known sentence of the folk which contains aphorism, truth, morals, and traditional views in a metaphorical, fixed and memorable form and which is passed down from generation to another". He also denotes to some proverbs which refer to the definition of proverbs for example "proverbs are the children of experience". "proverbs are the aphorism of the streets, and "proverbs are true words" " proverbs are bear a lot of common sense, experience, wisdom, and truth and they represent ready-made According to Barajas (2010), proverbs are expressions that are framing by contradictions because they are sage expressions that refer to something palpable to express things that are not specific. Furthermore, the obscure proverbs do not weaken them but allow them to become popular social aphorisms. Moreover, despite proverbs being considered popular expressions, few people can use them correctly in conversations with social and linguistic skills. In addition, although proverbs have fixed forms, their meanings could be changed according to the interpretation of particular social factors and settings.

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Meider(1985, P.119) has defined proverbs as “ a short, useful phrase well-known to the people, which contains statements of truth, morals, and traditional points of view in a figurative, fixed, and unforgettable form that are passed down through generations”.

He points out some proverbs that define proverbs, such as: proverbs are children of experience, proverbs are the saying of the street, and proverbs are true speech. Proverbs carry a lot of common sense, experience, wisdom and truth. They represent traditional strategies ready in works of oral speech, writings, high literature and the media (ibid.3-4).

However, Norrick (1985, P.78) has suggested the coming definition of proverb” A proverb is a traditional, conversational and didactic type with a free and possible general meaning with inflection, and preferably a metaphorical meaning.

The origin of the proverbs

According to Marvin (1922, P.4), The origin of the proverb is unknown. These books were earlier. Disraeli says” In ancient times, there were unwritten moral laws. The nation's proverbs precede its literature, and it is impossible to follow it back to its beginnings”. They emerge from unknown sources and increase in size as they continue. Everyone adopted it unconsciously as it came into existence.

Regarding the roots of proverbs Meider (2004) the salient paremiologist, mentioned that: proverbs like riddles, (jokes), or fairy tales, do not fall out of the sky, and neither are they products of a mythical soul of folk. Instead, they are always coined by an

Individuals either intentionally or unintentionally, as expressed in Lord John Russell’s well-known one-line proverb definition that has been taken on a proverbial status of kinds, ”a proverb is the wit of one and the aphorism of many”. Today, with the incredible power of mass media, a newly formulated proverb-like statement might become a bona fide proverb relatively quacking by way of radio, television, and print media. As with verbal folklore in general, the authentic statement might well be varied a bit as it gets picked up and becomes ever more an anonymous proverb whose wording, structure, style, and metaphor are such that it is memorable.

Merits of Proverbs

Different ideas for proverbs have been proposed by many prominent scholars in the field of proverbs. Here are the perceptions of two prominent scholars who will be referred to as Norrick(1985:32-34). He brings together the various features suggested by various scholars and has absorbed them. The following elements help in identifying the proverbs from other similar proverbs, these merits as follows:-

Conservative Proverbs: Sellar argued that proverbs should be conservative, meaning that none of their basic grammatical units can be replaced. In Norrick's Word, Seiler introduces just this definitional criterion for distinguishing proverbs from proverbial phrases. In reference to these characteristics of Norrick's words, proverbial phrases such as "face the music" and "the brow is like a mulberry" are immediately excluded from the category of proverbs because The lack of specifically basic grammatical units. They can therefore be replaced at will. Proverbs are the default. Perhaps Abraham is more precise in requiring that a proverb be a complete statement. Proverbs are (grammatical) sentences. Taylor specifies that proverbs be complete

(if elliptical) sentences. Moreover, writers such as Abraham, Honlick, and Maeder also accept the status of the complete sentence as an occasion for a proverb, and proverbs are an imitation that is closely linked to the traditional style of proverbs and to their status as folkloric elements. Another scholar who mentioned some of the virtues of proverbs is Trench(1853:16-17), who mentioned three things that enter into the formation of a proverb, which is shortness. , meaning, and humor. According to Trench, a short proverb (is eloquent, and when a proverb is short, it is intense in its breath). He points out that it is absolutely certain that a good proverb will be short and is compatible with complete transmission.

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These merits are elaborated on briefly:

a. Shortness (Rhetoric) According to Trench, "the proverb should be short and the breathing should be condensed." He points out that it is absolutely certain that a good proverb will be short and consistent with the complete and forcible conveying of its truth, humor and wit. This spirit will be prominent in the proverb, and it will consist of two, three and four words, and these words are sometimes single. Passage and these advantages are evident in short proverbs. Moreover, it is stated that brevity is only a relative term, and it may be more accurate to say that the proverb should be condensed to the smallest possible number of words and condense the basic aphorism, but if this condition is met. In order for it to be as short as possible, it should not be too short.

b. Trench states that "meaning must sometimes be sacrificed for the sake of alliteration.

c. Humor in proverbs Trench says, "A proverb must contain humor, that is, in addition to its good meaning, it must be in a style and appearance that is not harsh and harsh, and it must have a prick in it, so that it does not fall from memory lightly. Proverbs have been called tears of humanity not because they are sad, as many They are joyful, not because they are depressing, because many are full of laughter, but because many appeared when people's lives were discontented by the threat of injury and deprivation.

Arora (1984), in her article, scrutinized the stylistic characteristics of proverbs as follows:-

1. Alliteration (forgive and forget) اعفو وسامح
2. Resemblance (nothing ventured, nothing gained) غامر ولم يكسب شيئا
3. Rhyme (when the cat is away, the mice will play) عندما تغيب القطاة تلعب الفئران
4. Ellipsis (once bitten, twice shy) لدغة مرة والحذر مرتين

She also proposed some internal characteristics of proverbs which are as follows

- a. Hyperbole (all is fair in love and war) كل شيء عادل في الحب والحرب
- b. Paradox (for there to be peace there must first be war) لكي يكون هنالك سلام يجب ان تكون هناك حرب اولاً
- c. Personification (hunger is the best cooker) الجوع طبخ ماهر

Compilation of Proverbs

Various categorizations of proverbs have been suggested by many scholars, here are two main categorizations the first compilation is one outlined by Norrick (in Honeck, 1997:130-135), who developed a more practical- oriented and less luxurious schematization that categorizes proverbs according to the form of figuration they use. He differentiates five forms of figurative proverbs.

1. Synecdoche
2. Metaphoric
3. Metonymic.
4. Hyperbolic
5. Paradoxical

It must be mentioned that in Norrick's words, figurative proverbs have figurative meanings that vary from their literal meaning.

The Strategy of translating proverbs

Translating proverbs lays a big burden upon the translator, so the translator should know the linguistic and non-linguistic features of both languages. Linguistic features mean those elements that are not transformed only through words, what is important here is culture. Each proverb transforms a specific meaning in a specific context or situation. Therefore, a proverb should be rendered with care to bear the same cultural conventions as an authentic proverb. It is not rational to translate a proverb while just looking at the first meaning of its words in a dictionary. So many scholars stated that proverbs cannot be translated literary (word-for-word), and they may sometimes have no natural equivalent in the TL. Mollanar (2001, P.54), in translating proverbs between Parisian and English language suggested two strategies in translating proverbs

a- Some similar proverbs can be found in the two languages with more or less similar form, vocabulary, and meaning.

b- Many proverbs may be found in the two languages which have similar meanings and can be applied

in the same contexts, but they have different types and vocabulary.

While Beekman and Callow (in Gorjian, 2006), proposed three ways of translating proverbs

- 1- The words following the proverb could be introduced as having the same meaning as the proverb.
- 2- It can be replaced with an equivalent local proverb.
- 3- Its non-figurative meaning could be stated directly forwardly.

As far as the translation of the proverb is concerned Falk (1978, P.44), said

“Since idioms, proverbs, and certain non-productive compounds must be entered in the lexicon of a grammar as single units as if they were single morphemes, it is not surprising that these items confuse difficulties when translation from one language to another is involved”

Finally, Duff (ibid), emphasized that if there is no appropriate equivalent in TL, the translator should not force it into the translation.

Vinay and Derbelnet (1995, P.342), believed that the TL equivalents should “reproduce the same situation as the authentic, whilst using completely different wording”. This method can be used to preserve the stylistic effect of the SL text in the TL text. According to these scholars, an equivalent is an appropriate method when the translator has to deal with proverbs, idioms, clichés, nominal or adjectival phrases, and the onomatopoeia of animal sounds.

Data Analysis and Discussion

Data analysis, evaluation, and exegesis of data were collected through the questionnaire from 50 respondents who represent the students’ community, and the test from 20 students who represent the students’ community in Sudanese Universities. The methodology described provided a baseline for data collecting. The presentation of data is systematically linked to the format of the questionnaire and the written test related in the appendix. The following will be used to analyze data: description of the results. This chapter will concentrate on the analysis and explanation of data that was gathered for this study. Data analysis requires that the analyst divide the data into small constituents to obtain answers to research questions and to the test hypotheses. The questions of the study were mentioned as follows:

1. How best do students use the dictionary for increasing vocabulary and pronunciation?
2. What are the appropriate strategies for solving the problems of translating proverbs?
3. What are the problems encountered by EFL students in translating proverbs?
4. Why do great orators resort to proverbs in their speech?

The purpose of exegesis of the data is to bring it to an understandable and interpretable form so that the relations of the research problems can be studied and tested, and a conclusion drawn. On the other hand, when the researcher explains the research results, the researcher studies them for their meaning. This study aims to investigate the problems encountered by EFL students in translating English proverbs into Arabic language.

The Response to the Questionnaire

The responses to the questionnaire were 10 items and the test was 10 items. Fifty students have participated in the questionnaire and twenty have participated in the test. The following is the analytical explanation and discussion of the findings concerning the various points linked to the objectives and hypotheses of the study. Each item in the questionnaire was analyzed statistically and discussed. The following tables will support the discussion.

Table 1

Statement	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	df	Sig	reality Of 0.05	Value
1	2.4800	.61412	5.527	49	.001	significance	Agree
2	2.8000	.45175	12.522	49	.001	significance	Agree
3	2.7800	.54548	10.111	49	.001	significance	Agree
4	2.6200	.66670	6.576	49	.001	significance	Agree

Research Journal Of English(RJOE)

ISSN:2456-2696;An International Peer-Reviewed and Refereed Journal;Impact Factor:8.16 (SJIF)

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Statement number 1 in the above table stated that analyzing the speech of prophets and wise people helps students in translating proverbs, according to statistical analysis the students responded agreed and the reliability of the phrase was positive, the value of the (T-test) was (5.527) and the degree of freedom was (49) added to the value of the probability was (.001) that means the agreement of respondents on this statement. The std error was (.61412). The percentage of agreeing was (98%). This statement was intended to formulate the student's opinion about analyzing the speech of prophets and wise people help students in translating proverbs and. From the statistical analysis it can be indicated that this statement goes in the track of the study hypotheses that Sudanese university EFL learners lack analyzing the speech of prophets and wise people. Whenever, students know how to analyze the speech of prophets and wise people properly then certainly they will render correctly.

In the same table which was mentioned above, the statement number 2 which said adapting a procedure which allow the students to strike suitable balance between degree of accuracy

Of translation and the degree of readability for the target text is needed. With referring to the table above and statistical analysis which showed that the student's responded the majority agreed, the reliability of the statement was positive and the value test (T. test) was (12.522), and the value of the probability was .001. The (std) of this statement was .45175 at the level of significance 0.05. The percentages of those who agreed were (98%), and those who were neutral were (2%), and the total percentage of this phrase was 100%. It can be formulated from the above table that the majority of the students agreed that adapting a procedure which allows the students to strike suitable balance between the degree of accuracy of translation and the degree of readability for the target text is needed, so using this procedure by students and agreed thereof upon, lead to render text in accurate way certainly.

Statement number 3 which reads students use of a good advanced dictionary makes them accustomed too many examples and proverbs. Denoting to the table 4-1 mentioned above and statistical analysis the value of(T-test) calculated (10.111) degree of freedom (49) and the value of probability (.001), which means that there is statistical significance of the statistical reality elicited from the term that says students use of a good advanced dictionary makes them accustomed too many examples and proverbs. It is clear from the reality of statistical inference approval subjects of this phrase moderately at the significance level of (0.05), and the std defaults are (.54548). The percentage of agree is (98%). This statement was intended to educe the student's opinion about using a good advanced dictionary while rendering a text, and from the statistical analysis this statement is in line of the study hypotheses. Whenever, students use a good advanced dictionary then surely they will be accustomed to many terms, phrases and proverbs, which help them in translating proverbs.

Statement number 4, which mentioned in table 4-1 above, this statement, says knowing the correct pronunciation facilitates translating proverbs simultaneous and consecutive translation. Indicating to statistical analysis that the students responded agreed and reliability of the phrase is positive, so the value of (T-test) calculated (6.576) and the degree of freedom (49) and the value probability (0.001), which means that there is statistical significance of statistical reality conclusion of the phrase that says knowing the correct pronunciation facilitates translating proverbs simultaneous and consecutive translation. It is explicit from the reality of statistical inference approval subject of this phrase moderately at significance level of (0.05), and the mistakes are (.66670). The percentage of agree is (98%). As this statement directed to take the opinion of the students about it. From this statistical analysis it can be observed that this statement is in the track of the study hypotheses. So when students resort to pronounce the words correctly they will translate smoothly in simultaneous and consecutive translation.

Table 2

statement	Mean	Std. Deviation	Test Value = 2			reality Of Value 0.05	Agree
			T	df	Sig		
5	2.6200	.56749	7.725	49	.001	significance	Agree

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6	2.8000	.45175	12.522	49	.001	significance	
7	2.8000	.40406	14.000	49	.001	significance	Agree
8	2.6600	.51942	8.985	49	.001	agree	Agree

Showing the results phrase number 5 which reads appropriate strategies in teaching proverbs enable students to differentiate between the literal meanings and subtle meanings, clarified in the table above, the value of (T-test) calculated is (7.725), and the degree of freedom (49), the value of probability is (.001), which means that there is statistical significance of the statistical reality conclusion of the term that says appropriate strategies in teaching proverbs enable the students to differentiate between the literal meanings and subtle meanings. It is clear from the reality of statistical inference consent subjects of this phrase moderately at the significance level of (0.05). Thus it means that respondents were agreed thereof, upon this statement, so the percentage is (98%), and std errors are (.56749). From statistical analysis it can be said that this statement goes with the hypotheses of the study. However, if there is a good utilize of appropriate strategies in teaching proverbs and idioms it will be easy for the students to differentiate between the literal meanings and the subtle meanings.

Statement number 6 which says suitable strategies in teaching proverbs reinforce the knowledge of the students, denoting to the table mentioned above, the value of (T-test) accounted is (12.522), and the degree of freedom is (49), and the value of probability is (.001), which means that there is statistical significance of statistical reality deduction of the phrase that reads suitable strategies in teaching proverbs reinforce the knowledge of the students. It is obvious from the reality of statistical inference approved of this term moderately at significance level of (0.05). The respondents agreed are (49), and the percentage is (98%), while the std errors are (.45175). Indicating to statistical analysis it can be said that this term goes with the hypotheses of the study. Whenever, there are suitable strategies in teaching proverbs it will strengthen the knowledge of the students and confirm their rendering in this purview.

Statement number 7 which reads using convenient strategies in teaching proverbs minimize the mistakes of translating proverbs. Referring to the table 4-2 above, the value of T-test) calculated is (14,000), while the degree of freedom is (49), and the value of probability is (.001), which means that there is statistical significance of statistical reality conclusion of the term that reads using convenient strategies in teaching proverbs minimize the mistakes of translating proverbs. It is clear from the reality of statistical inference approved of this statement at the significance of (0.05). Therefore, the respondents agree upon this statement, the percentage is very high (98%), and the std faults are (.40406). From statistical analysis it can be said that this statement is on the track of the hypotheses of the study. So when there are convenient strategies in teaching proverbs certainly it will reduce the mistakes of the students while translating in this field.

Statement number 8 which says using proverbs in the speech emphasizes the intended meaning, seen from the table above, the value of (T-test) accounted is (8.985), while the degree of freedom is (49), and the value of probability is (.001), which means that there is statistical significance of statistical reality conclusion of the term using proverbs in speech emphasizes the intended meaning. It is apparent from the reality of statistical inference approved of this phrase evenly at the significance level of (0.05). Hence, it means that the respondents agreed upon this statement with high percentage of (98%), while the std errors are (.51942). From statistical analysis it can be noticed that this statement is in line with the hypotheses of the study. Whenever, the students use proverbs in their speech it will assure the purposed meanings.

Table 3

statement	Mean	Std. Deviation	Test Value = 2			reality Of Value 0.05	Value
			T	df	Sig		
9	2.8600	.45221	13.448	49	.001	significance	agree
10	2.6400	.56279	8.041	49	.001	significance	agree

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ISSN:2456-2696;An International Peer-Reviewed and Refereed Journal;Impact Factor:8.16 (SJIF)

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11	2.4800	.54361	6.244	49	.001	significance	agree
12	2.4000	.67006	4.221	49	.001	significance	agree

Statement number 9 in this table which reads translating proverbs in an accurate way makes the meaning of the target text clear. Shown from this table which mentioned above, the value (T-test) accounted is (13.448), while the degree of freedom is (49), and the value of probability is (.001), which means that there is statistical significance of statistical reality inference from the term translating proverbs in an accurate way makes the meaning of the target text clear. It is evident from the reality of statistical inference approved of this phrase moderately at the significance level of (0.05). Thus, it means that the respondents agreed upon this statement with high percentage of (98%), while the std mistakes are (, 45221). From statistical analysis it is clear that this statement it goes with the hypotheses of the study. When the students translate accurately, it makes the target text readable and quite obvious.

Statement number 10 which says reading a lot about proverbs leads to an accurate translation. From the results which are shown the table 4-3 mentioned above. The value (T-test) calculated is (8,041), while the degree of freedom is (49), and the value of probability is (.001), which means that there is statistical significance of statistical reality taken from the phrase reading a lot about proverbs leads to an accurate translation. It is obvious from the reality of statistical inference approved of this phrase evenly of significance level at (0.05). That means the respondents agree upon this statement of percentage of (98%), while the std errors are (, 56279). From statistical analysis it is apparent that this statement it is in line with the hypotheses of the study. So when the students read a lot about proverbs they may have acquired a lot of knowledge in this field which make them translate easily and correctly.

Table 4: Participants' Translation Performance in the English- Arabic Test

English Statement	Correct answer		Acceptable answer		Wrong answer		No. answer	
	Frequency	Percent	frequency	percent	frequenc y	percent	frequency	Percent
Statement 1	16	80%	0	0	4	20%	0	0
Statement 2	18	90%	0	0	0	0	2	10%
Statement 3	5	25%	0	0	1	5%	14	70%
Statement 4	17	85%	0	0	0	0	3	15%
Statement 5	7	35%	0	0	10	50%	3	15%
Statement 6	5	25%	0	0	11	55%	4	20%
Statement 7	5	25%	0	0	5	25%	10	50%
Statement 8	15	75%	2	10%	2	10%	1	5%
Statement 9	12	60%	3	15%	0	0	5	25%
Statement 10	13	65%	0	0	3	15%	4	20%

Discussions and Recommendations

Discussion Related to the first Question

“What are the appropriate strategies for solving the problems of translating proverbs?”

The strategies that used by the students while translating English proverbs were varied according to their knowledge and culture and it based on many criteria and the optimal use of the strategies in translating proverbs is to find the equivalents for the proverb which need to be translated. The first criteria is to use the convenient strategies for translating proverbs many students opt to use literal translation or word- for- word translation, this referred to their lack of knowledge about the strategies that used in translating proverbs which results in mistranslating the proverbs, beside changing the meaning of text and provided the target readers with wrong message, moreover, there was no suitable pedagogy in teaching proverbs in universities or higher secondary schools which causes many problems for students while come across proverbs in addition to the cultural barriers that confronted the students. They tend to render literally without given explanation or footnote which result in nonsense as shown in the example (Don't cry over spilt milk), which translated as لاتندم على ما فاتت . Moreover, the findings also indicate that being aware of how to use translation strategies and techniques can ease the

mission of translators and students

The results also show that literal translation of proverbs result in most cases in poor or wrong translation. Hence, translators or students should provide TL equivalent and deal with the proverbs as one unit.

Discussion Related to the second Question

“Why do some students lack knowledge about proverbs?”

The results of this question show that being exposed to SL proverbs by reading more books in various fields of knowledge, newspapers and magazines, watching English series and film and taking courses in this field in English-speaking countries will enhance the knowledge and glare the gap between the SL and the TL culture. Also the results show that being interested in proverbs by resorting to have knowledge about them will save the time for the students and the translators when they opt to translate in this field.

Discussion Related to the findings of the third Question

“Why do great orators resort to proverbs and idioms in their speech?”

The results of this question show that using more proverbs in speech leads to coherence and cohesion in speech and it strengthens the words of the speakers and orators. Also, it indicates that when the orators, speakers, and writers resort to using them because they are precisely worded and have great effects on the listeners and hearers. Besides these facts the orators and writers opt to use proverbs in their speech and writing to emphasizes their meaning and their texts and it gives their style the beauty which are needed in the speech or the text.

Conclusions

Arabic language and English language, unawareness of proverbs and the classification of idioms failure to find a target equivalent for the source language and lack of knowledge of pragmatic, formal and semantic merits of proverbs and idioms. Students and experts itemized on the facts behind these problems and through their answers it is obvious that insufficiency of realization of the source language cultural paradigm (traditions, habits, customs, ceremonies, social style and religious traditions and background), unawareness of cultural variances, and the propensity to use literal translation that is in most cases is not accurate, using the paraphrasing technique rather than giving the target language equivalence and the use of proverbs and idioms in colloquial rather than standard language are major reasons behind the failure in rendering proverbs correctly.

Recommendations

This study sheds light on some of the problems that encountered by EFL University students in translating English proverbs. Based on the findings of the study, here are some recommendations

- 1-EFL students should have competency and knowledge of both cultures.
- 2-EFL students and translators should adopt strategies according to the need motivation and purpose.
- 3-EFL students and translators should know the differences between the source language and the target language that enable them to be familiar with proverbs.
- 4-EFL students and translators should read different translations of different kinds of texts to enliven the task.
- 5-EFL students and translators should be aware of registers, dialects and socio-lect which create problems in translation.
- 6-EFL students and translators should have considerations of socio-linguistic elements, cultural aspects, linguistics and stylistic as well as some specific meta-lingual factors.

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Research Journal Of English(RJOE)

ISSN:2456-2696;An International Peer-Reviewed and Refereed Journal;Impact Factor:8.16 (SJIF)

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How to cite this article?

Abdeladie Ahmed Ibrahim, Yassir Elgailani Ahmed, Dr. Abdelrahman Mohammed Elhassan Hamid,“Problem Encountered by EFL University Students in Translation English Proverbs”Research Journal Of English (RJOE)9(2),PP:112-122,2024, DOI:10.36993/RJOE.2024.9.2.122